

EAASI IN PRACTICE: EMULATION USE CASES FROM AUSTRALIA

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Abstract – Australian Research Council LIEF funded project “The Australian Emulation Network: Accessing Born Digital Cultural Collections” brings together Australian GLAM institutions to undertake disk imaging and software emulation to provide access for research. Members of our AusEAASI Community of Practice (CoP) will present case studies of their institution’s use of the Australian instance of Emulation-as-a-Service Infrastructure (EAASI).

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I. INTRODUCTION

The collaborations engendered by *The Australian Emulation Network* project [1] bring together GLAM archivists, curators, and researchers in biweekly AusEAASI CoP meetings where we discuss our preservation challenges and achievements. This collaboration, around the shared digital infrastructure of EAASI, has led to many ingenious

emulation solutions. The panel will share details of some of their emulation projects.

II. BEN ABBOTT (ACMI)

ACMI is Australia’s national museum of screen culture with a permanent collection of diverse moving image material. Through the EAASI Network, we have demonstrated online accessibility for a selection of early videogames and interactive media art in our collection by embedding emulation environments directly into our public website. Functionality of some emulations will differ compared to that of original hardware, however this is often an acceptable compromise for accessibility.

III. BRYONY CAVALLARO, (SLNSW)

The State Library of New South Wales has preserved over 3,000 carriers encompassing both published and unpublished collections. A significant portion of these carriers contain materials that require

specialized software for access. Using the EAASI platform, the library has demonstrated emulated access to titles such as family history databases originally developed for outdated operating systems like Windows XP. EAASI has provided an opportunity to highlight the benefits of digital preservation activities undertaken within the Library.

IV. SALLY O'CALLAGHAN (NAA)

The National Archives of Australia sought to use our partnership with AusEAASI to pilot a data recovery and emulation project with 13 Mac formatted floppy disks. Training in disk imaging and configuring emulation environments in the Digital Heritage Lab enabled us to recover and access the content. Although the sample is small, taking this content from the beginning to the end of the process has enabled us to integrate and establish solutions for collection material with such complex dependencies, leveraging knowledge from others in the field.

V. FELIPE OLIVARES (AGNSW)

At AGNSW, the Digital Preservation, Time-Based Art Conservation, and Archives teams have come together to collaboratively address the challenges of preserving and accessing interactive media artworks from the 1990s. Our case studies come from two recently acquired archives containing prominent early examples of interactive art, held on obsolete carriers, mostly CD-ROMs and floppy disks. Using EAASI, we have been able to emulate and bring back to life a significant number of these works. A small selection is currently hosted on a WordPress website, which has become a key access point for internal stakeholders who may be interested in their re-display as historical artefacts.

VI. BEATRICE ZHANG (UNIVERSITY OF MELBOURNE)

At the University of Melbourne, we have been exploring the emulation of architectural archives using AusEaaS. We have built a series of emulation environments focused on recovering early digital materials created by Bill Mitchell—including *Topdown*, one of the earliest known CAD files, PowerPoint presentations and image files stored in now-obsolete formats. By recreating legacy Macintosh environments within EAASI, we are providing architectural historians with access to interpret digital artefacts no longer readable through

conventional tools. While EAASI provided a functional emulation platform, the process also revealed ongoing challenges with compatibility, metadata loss, and dependencies.

VII. CONCLUSION

The AusEAASI project has trained GLAM staff, with the CoP enabling them to learn together and build a community with ongoing conversations across institutions, in the service of providing access to born digital cultural heritage. Previously inaccessible content is now emulated in house for researchers to use, enabling engagement with media arts, games, architecture and other born digital cultural heritage artefacts with complex dependencies.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Swalwell, "The Australian Emulation Network: Accessing Born Digital Cultural Collections," in *Proceedings of the Second Summit on New Media Art Archiving*, Barcelona, 2022, pp. 40–45. <http://hdl.handle.net/1959.3/471461>

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